

PAPERMAKING PILOT TRIALS WITH A NEW SILICA COATED PCC FILLER

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ABSTRACT

In papermaking it is usual to use fibers, mineral fillers and sizing and retention agents, especially for printing and writing papers. Mineral fillers, such as calcium carbonate or clay, bring many benefits not only to the final product, since better paper properties are achieved (such as brightness, opacity, printability), but also to the process, since paper is easier to dry. Nevertheless, the main advantage of mineral fillers is their reduced cost when compared to fibers and for this reason its content in paper has been increased over the years – nowadays values of 25-30% can be found. However, the use of fillers has a detrimental effect on paper strength since they interfere with the fiber-to-fiber bonding network in the sheet, and leads to problems of retention and, as a consequence, formation and also printing problems (sheet delamination, picking, linting, dusting). The filler content is therefore limited. However, this drawback can be overcome by the modification of the fillers surface with compounds that promote a better bonding between the filler and the fibers. The authors modified the surface of precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) with silica produced in situ by hydrolysis of tetraethyl orthosilicate (silica precursor) in ethanol/water solutions under alkaline conditions. The papermaking potential of the new PCC materials as fillers was evaluated in laboratory and compared to that of unmodified PCC. An improvement of the paper strength properties was found by using about 28% of filler particles consisting of a composite of PCC with 30 wt% of silica. For example, an increase of 8% and 12% for the tensile and burst indices was found when compared to handsheets produced with the reference unmodified PCC. The papermaking results suggest that a silica film coating the calcium carbonate crystals may be beneficial for the fiber-to-filler bonding. In order to verify the efficiency of the PCC-silica composite, pilot trials were performed (a 0.5 m width paper web was produced at 1m/min) both with the modified and the unmodified fillers. Compared to the lab handsheets, the pilot results show even much higher increments in the tensile and burst indices when using the PCC-silica composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Printing and writing fine papers represents close to 33% of the total paper and board production in Europe [1]. These paper grades should exhibit excellent optical properties, good dimensional stability under different hygro-thermal conditions and the paper web should have enough wet and dry tensile strength enabling to be produced at speeds up to 1500 m/min, using the best available paper technology. The high paper opacity and relatively high static rigidity required oblige preserving the paper bulk, which is not in favour of intensive refining and, as a consequence, the wet web strength can be a limiting parameter. Therefore, pulp fibers with good optical and mechanical performance are required. The fibers from bleached kraft Eucalyptus globulus pulp have excellent morphological

properties to produce these paper grades, due to their intermediate fiber length and fiber width and a relatively high fiber wall thickness to fiber width ratio, which lead to a high specific surface area and a partial fiber collapse [2]. However, in addition to fibers, and for economical and functional reasons, the production of printing and writing papers requires fillers, which reduce the cost and contribute to increase opacity, sizing agents to delay the water penetration, and starch and others functional additives. Precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) is becoming the most common filler for the production of printing and writing fine papers. Besides contributing for the reduction of the fiber content, thus decreasing the dependence of forestry resources, it promotes drainage and drying in the paper machine, with clear benefits in terms of costs. On the other hand, some paper end-use properties, like brightness, opacity, gloss, smoothness and printability are usually enhanced and its impact is often superior to that of other fillers. However, as expected, the calcium carbonate mineral particles, as the other fillers, cause a decrease in fiber bonding, which leads to a reduction of the paper strength. Additionally, it increases the demand of internal sizing agents and the phenomena of abrasion, dusting and bad filler retention. Therefore, the filler content in paper is limited to values usually not superior to 25% [3-5]. In order to overcome some of these drawbacks and increase the filler content some treatments/modifications of the filler surface have been suggested. Precipitated calcium carbonate has been treated/modified by organic compounds such as starch, starch derivatives, carboxymethylcellulose, among others [6-10]. For instance, an increase in filler incorporation without loss in tensile strength and brightness was reported by Gill [10] using a cationic polymer surface modified PCC. In addition, several authors claim the positive effect of the modification of PCC with starch and other polysaccharides on the paper properties [6-7,9]. Some work has been also developed aiming to obtain calcium carbonate-based filler with improved acid-resistant properties which are required for papermaking in weakly acid to neutral conditions [11]. Nevertheless, just a few studies include the evaluation of the impact of the treated fillers on the mechanical properties of the papers [5,12,13]. In general, when comparing the handsheets made with the inorganics-treated fillers *vs.* those based on the untreated filler, typically mechanical properties (tensile index, burst index) have not improved but a few optical properties such as brightness and, in some cases, the light scattering coefficient have been enhanced.

Recently, the authors of the present paper reported the production of silica at the surface of PCC by hydrolysis of tetraethyl orthosilicate (silica precursor) in ethanol/water solutions under alkaline conditions [14]. In the new modified particle it was proved that silica was fixed to the PCC particles in the form of a film and that the amount of silica in the new materials could be controlled based on the ammonia concentration of the reaction medium, among other factors. It was suggested that hydroxyl groups present at the surface of silica-coated PCC could provide stronger physical interactions with the cellulosic fibers than those observed with unmodified PCC and thus could improve fiber-filler interactions and paper strength [14]. In another paper of the same authors this hypothesis was confirmed; in fact, the incorporation of silica-coated PCC fillers led to increase of tensile index, tear index and internal cohesion, in comparison with the corresponding paper with unmodified PCC filler [15]. These important results were explored by increasing the filler content of the paper while preserving good strength properties [16]. The present work aims to further investigate the potential of silica-coated PCC particles to be used at pilot scale, comparing the results with those obtained at lab scale with the same furnish. For that, a pilot paper machine was used, using as a reference the unmodified PCC particles.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 PCC modification

Industrial scalenohedral PCC and silica-coated PCC particles were used as fillers in the present work. The silica-coated PCC particles were obtained from dry PCC, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), water, ethanol, and ammonia as reported in detail by Gamelas et al. [14]. The experimental conditions to produce the modified PCC's, with a silica content of 30 %, as well as the methods to evaluate the particles size, surface charge (zeta potential) and brightness, were previously published elsewhere [15].

2.2 Handsheets production and papermaking properties

An industrial *Eucalyptus globulus* bleached kraft pulp refined up to 32 °SR was used as the cellulosic fiber source. After disintegration it was diluted to a consistency of 1% in demineralized water. Aqueous suspensions of the unmodified or modified PCC's containing 1 wt% of filler were prepared by adding water to PCC and stirring magnetically (20 min) and in the case of the laboratory tests also using ultrasounds (15 min, 50 KHz), before use. Alkenyl succinic anhydride (ASA) supplied by the industry was used as the internal sizing agent after stabilization by adding it to a 3% starch suspension standing at 60 °C, which was prepared as previously reported elsewhere [17]. A 0.025% aqueous solution of a linear cationic polyacrylamide (L-CPAM) was prepared by dissolving the solid at 40°C in demineralized water and used as retention agent.

Handsheets were produced in two batch laboratory sheet formers: a) former A (255/SA model, MAVIS), 120 mesh screen and air agitation; b) former B (SCA, SCAN standard), 100 mesh screen and manual agitation. In both cases, the aim was to obtain a basis weight of 80g/m² and a target filler content in the handsheets close to 27 wt%. The amounts added (wt%) were 68.9, 30.0, 1.0, 0.1 and 0.02 for fiber, filler, starch, ASA and retention agent, respectively. A mixture of the fiber suspension (400 mL) with the PCC suspension (100 mL) was prepared in a beaker. After 120 seconds of mechanical stirring, the starch/ASA mixture (at *ca.* 60 °C) was added. The retention agent (4 mL) was finally added after a total time of 290 seconds and allowed to stir for more 5 seconds. The mixture was transferred into the former and after 10 seconds of agitation, decantation and drainage were performed. The total contact time of the retention agent with the other components in the mixture was *ca.* 30 s. The sheets were collected from the web and pressed, dried and conditioned according to the ISO 5269-1 standard. At least two series of experiments were run for each formulation. The structural (basis weight, thickness, density, bulk and air permeability), mechanical (tensile, stiffness, tear and burst resistance) and optical (light scattering, opacity, brightness) properties were measured according to the corresponding ISO Standard Test Methods.

2.3 Pilot paper machine web production

The pilot paper machine comprises three stock chests, a stock pump, a wire part, a couch roll, a press section and 5 dry cylinders operating at about 105°C (oil heaters), in addition to the vacuum pumps and auxiliary equipment and instrumentation. A continuous web of 0.5 m width was produced at a speed of 1 m/min, using also an industrial refined pulp with 32°SR. In the pilot tests, the refined pulp, the fillers and the starch with ASA were added to the stock chest at the beginning, considering the same amounts as those used for the lab handsheets, while the retention agent (L-CPAM) was added inline using a peristaltic pump at the suction of the stock pump. The contact time of the L-CPAM with the stock suspension was about 20 seconds.

The filler retention in the handsheets and in the pilot paper machine sheets was determined after calcination at 525 °C as described elsewhere [15].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Laboratorial data

Table 1 presents the experimental results obtained in the two lab formers. Two important differences between the handsheets were observed. On the one hand, the filler content was about 28.4% and 25.2%, respectively when the sheet formers A and B were used, which probably can be related with the screen nominal size opening of 125 µm and 149 µm, respectively. On the other hand, and as a consequence of the different filler retention and other hydrodynamic conditions in the sheet former, the apparent density of the papers produced were lower in the sheet former A. In accordance with the apparent density, the air permeability was higher and the mechanical properties (tensile index, tear index and burst index) smaller for the less dense papers (former A). No significant differences were observed between the two set of samples regarding the optical properties (light scattering,

opacity and brightness). Regarding the effect of the type of filler used in the paper production (PCC vs silica-coated PCC), important effects were observed. The burst index increased about 12% when the silica-coated PCC filler was used instead of the PCC filler, for the paper with apparent paper densities close to 0.66 g/cm^3 . The effect was lower for the paper with an apparent density of approximately 0.62 g/cm^3 . The tear index also increased when the modified fillers were used. Regarding the tensile index the results are not conclusive but suggest that the positive effect of the modified filler is revealed when the apparent paper density is lower. In fact, for the papers with apparent density of about 0.62 g/cm^3 , the tensile index increased from 38.3 N.m/g to 41.5 N.m/g , which represents an increment of 8.3%. In a previous paper [16] the tensile index was increased approximately 15%, from 27.2 N.m/g to 31.4 N.m/g . The results suggest that the influence of the modified filler increases when the fiber-to-fiber bonding ability is less developed. It is worth mentioning that the positive effect of the modified filler was obtained at the same paper bulk, an important property for writing and printing papers. Regarding the optical properties, both sets of results clearly indicate that the specific light scattering decreases markedly when the conventional PCC filler was replaced by the silica-coated PCC filler. These results suggest that the fiber/silica-coated PCC filler bonding ability is higher than that of the unmodified PCC filler, in agreement with previous results [15, 16].

Papermaking properties		Former A		Former B	
		PCC	PCC-Sil	PCC	PCC-Sil
Filler content	[%]	28.0	28.8	23.7	26.8
Filler retention	[%]	93.4	95.8	77.4	78.9
Basis weight	[g/m ²]	81.29	83.07	77.7	82.2
Paper density	[g/cm ³]	0.62	0.61	0.66	0.66
Paper bulk	[cm ³ /g]	1.62	1.63	1.52	1.52
Air permeability	[μm/Pa.s]	27.76	29.97	19.42	19.41
Burst index	[kPa.m ² /g]	2.17	2.31	3.07	3.46
Tensile index	[N.m/g]	38.34	41.53	41.36	41.6
T.E.A.	[J/m ²]	60.1	66.9	60.4	63.8
Tear index	[mN.m ² /g]	5.17	5.59	6.41	6.93
Light scattering coef.	[m ² /kg]	70.36	53.77	70.27	55.89
Opacity	[%]	89.97	87.11	89.97	87.97
Brightness R457	[%]	92.48	92.04	92.25	91.96

Table 1: Papermaking properties of handsheets produced with PCC and silica-coated PCC.

3.2 Pilot trials

A paper web was prepared in a first trial using the same pulp stock as that of the laboratorial handsheets (PM1). Besides, another trial was carried out with one year of interval and consequently with a different pulp stock but having the same °SR (PM2). The properties of the papers produced are summarized in Table 2. It should be mentioned that some operating difficulties were found especially in the first trial (PM1), resulting in the need to increase the basis weight. On the other hand, the apparent density of the paper web was unexpectedly low for both trials, suggesting the need to increase the pressure in the press section in future trials. As for the paper properties, the paper filler content and the corresponding filler retention are in the same range of those of the lab handsheets. However, in the first trial (PM1), the retention of the silica-coated PCC was slightly smaller than that of the unmodified PCC, which may be ascribed to the higher difficulty in dispersing the fillers. Regarding the mechanical properties, namely the tensile and the tear indices, a remarkable increase was detected when the PCC filler was replaced by the silica-coated PCC filler. Even considering the contribution of the different filler content (assuming a direct proportionality), the tensile index increases more than 20%, whatever the direction considered (machine direction (MD) vs cross direction (CD)), which clearly demonstrates the positive impact of the silica-coated PCC filler. As the

laboratorial data have suggested, the positive effect is particularly evident for less densified paper structures.

Paper properties		PM1		PM2	
		PCC	PCC-sil	PCC	PCC-sil
Filler content	[%]	28.6	25.9	26.6	26.7
Filler retention	[%]	95.2	86.3	88.7	89.0
Basis weight	[g/m ²]	109.5	107.5	90.7	89.03
Paper density	[g/cm ³]	0.42	0.40	0.48	0.46
Paper bulk	[cm ³ /g]	2.38	2.50	2.10	2.20
Air permeability	[μm/Pa.s]	46.4	47.9	78.40	77.91
Burst index	[kPa.m ² /g]	0.87	1.23	0.85	1.60
Tensile index (MD/CD)	[N.m/g]	20.2/14.9	28.0/20.3	20.6/18.8	36.6/23.5
T.E.A. (MD/CD)	[J/m ²]	26.9/18.5	64.4/32.7	8.3/17.2	44.3/34.1
Tear index	[mN.m ² /g]	3.9/3.5	5.6/5.5	-	-
Light scattering coef.	[m ² /kg]	71.57	53.69	77.05	54.01
Opacity	[%]	93.7	91.2	90.74	88.01
Brightness R457	[%]	90.8	90	91.23	90.90

Table 2: Paper properties of pilot paper sheets produced with PCC and silica-coated PCC.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The present work enabled to confirm, at pilot scale, the results obtained at laboratorial scale regarding the potential of silica-coated PCC filler to be used in papermaking. The mechanical handsheet properties (tensile, tear and burst indices) increased significantly when the PCC filler was replaced by the silica-coated PCC filler, at the same paper apparent density. The specific light scattering coefficient decreased with the silica-coated PCC filler suggesting the increase in the fiber-to-filler interactions. The positive effect of the modified PCC filler seems to be higher when the paper apparent density is lower. In fact, in the case of the papers produced in the pilot machine, which exhibit the lowest apparent density, the positive impact of the modified filler was much more pronounced than in the case of papers with higher apparent density. However, as the apparent density of the paper obtained in pilot machine were too low, a new pilot trial will be carried out in order to confirm this hypothesis.

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REFERENCES

- [1] CEPI, Key statistics, Confederation of European paper industry, 2013.
- [2] A. Santos, M. E. Amaral, A. Vaz, O. Anjos and R. Simões, Effect of *Eucalyptus globulus* wood density on papermaking potential, *Tappi J.*, **7(5)**, 2008, pp. 17-24.
- [3] L. Raymond, R. Turcotte and R. Gratton, The challenges of increasing filler in fine paper. *Paper Technology* 2004, July, pp. 34-40.
- [4] B., Thorp, Engineered fillers: an agenda 2020 goal. *Solutions! for People, Processes and Paper* 2005, May, pp. 45-48.
- [5] J. Shen, Z. Song, X. Qian and W. Liu, Modification of papermaking grade fillers: a brief review. *Bioresources*, **4**, 2009, pp. 1190-1209.

- [6] Y. Zhao, H. Zeshan, A. Ragauskas and Y. Deng, Improvement of paper properties using starch-modified precipitated calcium carbonate filler. *Tappi J.*, **2(4)**, 2004, pp. 3-7.
- [7] J. Shen, Z. Song and X. Qian, Investigations on the preparation of starch/sodium oleate/alum modified precipitated calcium carbonate filler and its use in papermaking. *Appita J.*, **62**, 2009, pp. 360-364.
- [8] J. Shen, Z. Song, X. Qian and F. Yang, Carboxymethyl cellulose/alum modified precipitated calcium carbonate fillers: preparation and their use in papermaking. *Carbohydr. Polym.*, **81**, 2010, pp. 545-553.
- [9] G. H. Fairchild, Treatment of inorganic filler material for paper with polysaccharides. US Patent 5,458,679, 1995.
- [10] R. A. Gill, Cationic polymer-modified filler material, process for its preparation and method. Canada Patent, 2037525, 1991.
- [11] J. D. Passaretti, Acid-stabilized calcium carbonate, process for its production and method for its use in the manufacture of acidic paper, US Patent 5,043,017, 1991.
- [12] J. Shen, Z. Song, X. Qian and W. Liu, A preliminary investigation into the use of acid-tolerant newspaper. *Bioresources*, **4**, 2009, pp. 1178-1189.
- [13] J. Shen, Z. Song, X. Qian and W. Liu, Modification of precipitated calcium carbonate filler using sodium silicate/zinc chloride based modifiers to improve acid-resistance and use of the modified filler in papermaking. *Bioresources*, **4**, 2009, pp. 1498-1519.
- [14] J. A. F. Gamelas, A. F. Lourenço and P. J. Ferreira, New modified filler obtained by silica formed by sol-gel method on calcium carbonate. *J Sol-Gel Sci Technol.*, **59**, 2011, pp. 25-31.
- [15] A. F. Lourenço, J. A. F. Gamelas, C. Zscherneck and P. J. Ferreira, Evaluation of silica-coated PCC as new modified filler for papermaking. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, **52**, 2013, pp. 5095-5099.
- [16] A. F. Lourenço, J. A. F. Gamelas and P. J. Ferreira, Increase of the filler content by using a silica-coated PCC filler. *Nordic Pulp and Paper Research Journal*, **29(2)**, 2014, pp. 240-245.
- [17] M. S. Saraiva, J. A. F. Gamelas, A. P. M. de Sousa, B. M. Reis, J. L. Amaral and J. P. Ferreira, A New Approach for the Modification of Paper Surface Properties Using Polyoxometalates. *Materials*, **3**, 2010, pp. 201-215.